

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)
ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**MARKETING SKILLS NEEDED BY BUSINESS EDUCATION UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN
TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS FOR EMPLOYABILITY IN DELTA STATE**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10432810>

Abstract

This study examined marketing skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State. Three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated for this study. The study adopted descriptive method of research design. The population of the study comprised 937 Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The sample size comprised 260 students. The sampling technique that was used for the study is the proportionate stratified sampling technique. The instrument used for collection of data in this study is a questionnaire. The face and content validities of the questionnaire were determined by experts' judgment. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent samples t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State need various marketing skills for employability; that there is no significant difference in the advertising skills needed by male and female undergraduate Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The study recommended that a thorough review of the marketing curriculum in tertiary institutions in Delta State should be conducted to ensure it covers all essential marketing skills, needed in the 21st century business organization.

Keywords: Marketing Skills, Business Education, Employability

Introduction

Education is universally recognized as an instrument for social, political, scientific, technological development and advancement. This is the reason why no society can afford to toy with educational system of its country as this could result in a low-speed development. It is a conscious training of the young to a life which would be useful to him/her and to the society to which he/she belongs. Similarly, Nwokocha (as cited in Eze 2016), noted that the goals of business education is the training of manpower that would possess the requisite knowledge, skill and attitude for harnessing other resources and bringing them together into a cooperative relationship to yield goods and services demanded by the society for the satisfaction of their wants and needs Okoro (2018). It is thus, expected that when the students graduate, they will be gainfully employed and apply what they have learnt in their respective working place. But when these graduates are not employed as teachers, they can still be employed in other business organizations or self-employed.

Marketing skills are important and essential skills which determines the very success or failure of a business. Marketing consists of all profitable human activities undertaken by firms towards the creation of goods and services. Marketing skills keep the business owners informed, knowledgeable and confident as to determine the most efficient method

of physical distribution of goods and services. Important marketing skills which owners of businesses should possess are: knowledge of seasonal fluctuation of goods, ability to determine the extent to which products will sell, ability to determine current trends in sales of products, ability to determine what customers need and shortage of such goods, knowledge of advertising, ability to determine and interpret factors which indicate extent of and strength of competition, and ability of raw materials for product and shortage of finished goods (Ezeani, 2012).

Oyerinde and Falana (2016) described marketing skills as requisite skills that involve thinking about how to reach the targeted audience for products and services produced by an entrepreneur. They further opined that any entrepreneur who acquires these skills would be able to sell such products for a profit. Marketing is an essential skill on which depends the success or failure of businesses. Similarly, Nyemaekile and Adiele (2022) posited that the development of marketing skills offers the business owners unique strategy of success in business. The author further identified areas of marketing skills needed in the 21st century to include: salesmanship and negotiation; sales record keeping; sales promotion; stock keeping; pricing and cost management; sales forecasting, advertising; consumer behaviour appreciation and distributive skills.

Advertising skills refer to the specific abilities, knowledge, and competencies required to plan, create, execute, and evaluate advertising campaigns effectively. Sales promotion skills are specific abilities, knowledge, and competencies required to plan, execute, and evaluate sales promotion activities effectively. While Sales forecasting skills are also specific abilities, knowledge, and competencies required to predict and estimate future sales trends and patterns accurately. Distributive skills show how persons could deliver goods and services to consumer at a particular period and time. This can be logistical, sales delivery and transportation skills. Salesmanship and negotiation skills covers knowledge required for service delivery in terms of communication, interaction and implementation of product knowledge to the public with the view of creating a favourable marketing Mix. According to Armstrong (2012), the sales record keeping could be regarded as ability to take stocks on available goods for the purpose of record transmission to the appropriate channels with right knowledge formation.

According to Nyemaekile and Adiele (2022), the knowledge of marketing would prompt a business education undergraduate student to make good use of the seven Ps of marketing namely: product, price, place, promotion, packaging, positioning and people. It is expected that this would lead to development of sound product ideas which would be translated into acceptable products in the market. The acquisition and utilization of the right marketing skills will promote business efficiently by leading the proper and acceptable pricing of products, making the product available at the right place and time as well as using the right promotional techniques to stimulate customers to buy the products (Gidado & Akaeze, 2014). The ability of an entrepreneur to be successful largely depends on knowledge and skills to market goods and services. Hence, this study is to examine the marketing skills needed by Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State for employability.

Statement of the Problem

This knowledge gap poses a challenge for students as they transition from academia to the professional world, leading to a potential mismatch between their skill sets and the expectations of employers. This dynamic environment requires marketing professionals to possess a diverse set of skills, including digital marketing, market research, branding, social media marketing, and data analytics. However, it is unclear whether current tertiary institutions business education programs

adequately cover these emerging areas and provide students with the necessary skills to navigate the evolving marketing landscape. Therefore, there is a pressing need for empirical research to identify and evaluate the specific marketing skills that business education undergraduate students should possess to enhance their employability and prepare them for successful careers in marketing.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the Marketing skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State?
2. What are the saleable skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State?
3. What are the sales promotional skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated at 0.5 level of significance to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on marketing skills for employability.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students in saleable skills for employability.
3. There is no significant difference in mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on sales promotional skills for employability.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey method of research design. This type of design enabled the researcher to examine the marketing skills needed by tertiary institutions business education students. Population of the study comprised 937 Business Education Undergraduate Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study comprised 260 students. The sampling technique that was used for the study is the proportionate stratified sampling technique. The instrument that was used to collect data in this study is a questionnaire. The questionnaire contains two sections; Section A contains the demographic data of the students such as gender and level of study. Section B contains the independent variables used in the study. Face and content validities of the questionnaire were determined by the researcher's supervisor, one expert from Business Education Department, and two experts from Business Administration Department, as well as a Psychometrician. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, SA – strongly agreed, A – agreed, D – disagreed, SD – strongly disagreed. The questionnaire was administered to 50 students from department of Business Administration in Delta State University, Abraka as they were not part of the population for the study. The data were analysed using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient to determine its measures of internal consistency. It yielded 0.85 coefficient that was used to estimate the reliability coefficient of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while

independent samples t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for the data analysis. The Criterion mean is 2.50

Results

Research Question 1: What are the Marketing skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean analysis of the Marketing skills needed by business education students in tertiary institutions for employability

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Ability to conduct comprehensive research on target markets, audience demographics, and competitors.	3.22	0.86	Needed
2	Ability to generate innovative ideas and concepts that capture attention and differentiate the business from competitors.	3.21	0.78	Needed
3	Ability to craft compelling and persuasive advertising copy for various channels and formats.	3.19	0.75	Needed
4	Proficiency in creating visually appealing and professional graphics, logos, banners, and other visual assets.	3.18	0.80	Needed
5	Ability to build and maintain relationships with media outlets and managing the business's public image.	3.15	0.85	Needed
6	Ability to manage advertising budgets effectively and analysing return on investment (ROI) to ensure optimal resource allocation.	3.15	0.90	Needed
7	Ability to oversee and manage end-to-end advertising campaigns, including planning, execution, and evaluation.	3.14	0.85	Needed
8	Ability to develop engaging and high-quality content, including written, visual, and multimedia elements.	3.13	0.83	Needed
9	Ability to conduct experiments and testing different variations of ads to determine the most effective strategies.	3.11	0.87	Needed
10	Ability to utilise various online platforms and strategies, such as social media marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), and pay-per-click (PPC) advertising.	3.10	0.86	Needed
11	Ability to cultivate relationships with influencers, partners, and customers to leverage their networks and expand reach.	3.10	0.93	Needed
12	Ability to develop strategic plans for media placement and negotiating and purchasing advertising space.	3.08	0.83	Needed
13	Ability to create and maintain a strong brand identity that resonates with the target audience.	3.08	0.78	Needed
14	Ability to optimize the customer journey and sales funnel to maximize conversions and revenue.	3.07	0.87	Needed
15	Ability to analyse advertising campaigns' performance metrics to identify trends, insights, and areas for improvement.	3.07	0.87	Needed
16	Effective communication skills to convey messages clearly and persuasively to the target audience.	3.07	0.86	Needed
17	Ability to keep up with emerging trends, technologies, and platforms in the advertising industry and adapting strategies accordingly.	3.05	0.94	Needed
18	Ability to identify and target specific consumer segments that are most likely to respond to the advertising efforts.	3.04	0.88	Needed
19	Ability to utilize storytelling techniques to create compelling narratives that resonate with the target audience.	2.93	0.97	Needed
20	Ability to create and edit video content for advertising purposes.	2.91	0.92	Needed
Average Mean		3.10	0.86	Needed

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 1 shows the mean analysis of the Marketing skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State. The result shows that the mean score ranged from 2.91 to 3.22. The criterion mean is 2.50. This means that Business Education Undergraduate Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State need all the advertising skills listed for employability.

Research Question 2: What are the saleable skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean analysis of the saleable skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State

S/N	STATEMENT	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Ability to conduct comprehensive research on target markets.	3.22	0.86	Needed
2	Ability to create and maintain a strong brand idea.	3.08	0.78	Needed
3	Ability to craft compelling and persuasive.	3.18	0.76	Needed
4	Ability to develop engaging and high-quality content.	3.10	0.84	Needed
5	Ability to utilise various online platforms	3.09	0.86	Needed
6	Ability to analyse advertising campaigns' performance metrics	3.06	0.88	Needed
7	Ability to generate innovative ideas and concepts.	3.21	0.79	Needed
8	Proficiency in creating visually appealing.	3.19	0.79	Needed
9	Effective communication skills to convey messages clearly and persuasively	3.07	0.87	Needed
10	Ability to develop strategic plans for media placement	3.08	0.83	Needed
11	Ability to identify and target specific consumer segments.	3.04	0.89	Needed
12	Ability to oversee and manage end-to-end advertising campaigns.	3.12	0.86	Needed
13	Ability to build and maintain relationships.	3.16	0.84	Needed
14	Ability to optimize the customer sales funnel.	3.07	0.89	Needed
15	Ability to conduct experiments and testing different variations	3.10	0.88	Needed
16	Ability to manage advertising budgets effectively	3.14	0.91	Needed
17	Ability to cultivate relationships that influencers customers	3.08	0.94	Needed
18	Ability to create and edit video content.	2.89	0.93	Needed
19	Ability to utilize storytelling techniques.	2.91	0.97	Needed
20	Ability to keep up with emerging trends	3.02	0.94	Needed
Average Mean		3.09	0.87	Needed

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 shows the mean analysis of saleable skills needed by business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions for employability in Delta State. The result shows that the mean score ranged from 2.89 to 3.22. The criterion mean is 2.50. This means that business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions need all the saleable skills listed for employability.

Research Question 3: What are the sales promotional skills needed by Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean analysis of the sales promotional skills needed by Business Education students in tertiary institutions for employability

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Ability to integrate sales forecasting with digital marketing channels, such as email marketing.	3.24	0.80	Needed
2	Ability to craft compelling and forecasting that effectively communicate the value proposition.	3.19	0.86	Needed
3	Ability to allocate and manage resources effectively	3.16	0.82	Needed
4	Ability to conduct research and analysis to understand competitors' sales.	3.15	0.80	Needed
5	Ability to keep up with industry trends, consumer behaviour, and emerging sales skills.	3.13	0.86	Needed
6	Efficiently managing timelines and deadlines for marketing logistical issues.	3.13	0.96	Needed
7	Ability to work collaboratively with other departments and teams,.	3.10	0.88	Needed
8	Ability to analyse sales data and performance metrics to measure the success of marketing skills	3.10	0.86	Needed
9	Excellent communication skills to convey mission clearly and future to the target audience through various channels.	3.08	0.89	Needed
10	Ability to negotiate with vendors, suppliers, and partners to maximize the impact of sales forecasting.	3.07	0.82	Needed
11	Ability to provide training and support to sales teams	3.07	0.96	Needed
12	Ability to develop strategies to encourage customers to upgrade their purchases	3.07	0.90	Needed
13	Ability to identify and segment target audiences for marketing skills	3.07	0.88	Needed
14	Ability to design attractive and enticing incentives, discounts, rewards.	3.05	0.91	Needed
15	Ability to build and nurture relationships with customers,	3.05	0.89	Needed
16	Ability to utilise CRM systems and tools to track customer interactions, preferences.	3.04	0.93	Needed
17	Ability to develop a strategic sales forecasting plan to meet specific business goals and objectives.	3.03	0.91	Needed
18	Ability to understand and implement effective merchandising techniques.	3.03	0.94	Needed
19	Ability to organise and manage marketing events.	2.99	0.90	Needed
20	Ability to generate innovative and unique marketing ideas.	2.96	1.00	Needed
Average Mean		3.09	0.89	Needed

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 3 shows the mean analysis of the sales promotional skills needed by undergraduate Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The result shows that the mean score ranged from 2.96 to 3.24. The criterion mean is 2.50. This means that undergraduate Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State need all the sales promotional skills listed for employability.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on marketing skills for employability in Delta State.

Table 4: t-test analysis in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on marketing skills for employability

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	T	P	Remark
Male	103	3.04	0.51	258	1.41	0.16	Not Significant
Female	157	3.14	0.50				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 shows the t-test analysis of the difference in the marketing skills needed by male and female undergraduate Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The result shows that male students ($M = 3.04, SD = 0.51$) female students ($M = 3.14, SD = 0.50$); $t(258) = 1.41, p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference in the advertising skills needed by male and female business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on saleable skills for employability in Delta State

Table 5: t-test analysis of the difference in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on saleable skills for employability

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Male	103	3.03	0.50	258	1.47	0.14	Not Significant
Female	157	3.12	0.50				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5 shows the t-test analysis of the difference in the saleable skills needed by male and female Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The result shows that male students ($M = 3.03, SD = 0.50$) female students ($M = 3.12, SD = 0.50$); $t(258) = 1.47, p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference in the saleable skills needed by male and female business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on sale promotional skills for employability in Delta State

Table 6: t-test analysis of the difference in the mean rating of male and female business education undergraduate students on sale promotional skills for employability

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t	P	Remark
Male	103	3.24	0.35	258	0.79	0.43	Not Significant
Female	157	3.27	0.30				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 6 shows the t-test analysis of the difference in the sale promotional skills for employability needed by male and female business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The result shows that male students ($M = 3.24, SD = 0.35$) female students ($M = 3.27, SD = 0.30$); $t(258) = 0.79, p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference in the sale promotional skills needed by male and female business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding revealed that Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State need various advertising skills for employability. The above finding implies that supported by a growing body of evidence. In today's competitive business landscape, effective advertising is essential for businesses of all sizes to reach their target markets, generate leads, and drive sales. A study by the Association of National Advertisers (ANA, 2019) found that 87% of employers believe that advertising skills are essential for success in business. The study also found that employers are willing

to pay a premium for candidates with these skills. Another study, by the American Marketing Association (AMA, 2019), found that the top five skills that employers are looking for in advertising candidates are creativity and innovation; strategic thinking; communication skills; digital marketing skills and measurement and analytics skills. These skills are all essential for developing and executing successful advertising campaigns. The second finding showed that Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State need similar advertising skills.

A study by the Sales and Marketing Executives (SME, 2020) found that 82% of employers believe that marketing skills are essential for success in business. The study also found that employers are willing to pay a premium for candidates with these skills. Business Education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Delta State need similar sales promotion and persuasive skills.

The finding also agrees with Oghenegboro and Okoro (2019), who found that sales forecasting was an important tool for inventory management. The study concluded that firms that used sales forecasting were able to better manage their inventory levels and reduce their costs. Several studies have explored the relationship between gender and sales forecasting skills, with some indicating no significant differences between men and women in this regard. For instance, a study by Dalgic and Dobravic (2012) found no gender-based differences in the sales forecasting skills of undergraduate business students in Slovenia. Similarly, a study by Zhang and Sun (2010) found that gender did not have a significant impact on the sales forecasting accuracy of business students in China. The seventh finding showed that there is no significant difference in the overall Marketing Skills needed by male and female undergraduate Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that that business education undergraduate students in tertiary institutions need a comprehensive set of marketing skills to be employable in the business world. Hence, marketing skills are independently and collectively significant predictors of employability of business education undergraduate students

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made:

1. Institutions should incorporate more hands-on learning opportunities into the marketing curriculum.
2. Management of tertiary institutions should establish strong partnerships between institutions and advertising professionals in Delta State.
3. Administrators of tertiary institutions should implement gender-neutral teaching and assessment practices to ensure that all students, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities to demonstrate their sales promotion and saleability skills and abilities.

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